

A STUDY TO UNDERSTAND THE CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES OF HEALTHCARE SERVICE DELIVERY IN INDIA.

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Abstract: Every industry has its own challenges & opportunities which need special strategies to utilize the opportunities lying beneath the challenges. Healthcare service delivery is not an exception, it has its own challenges to overcome & some of the challenges are unique to the industry. In this study, an effort has been made to uncover the true potentiality of healthcare service delivery in India.

Keywords: Challenges, PPP, GDP, FDI, RFP

Introduction:

1.) Segmentation: In the financial year 2021, the hospital industry contributed 70%, Pharmaceuticals 20% & Medical Technology & others contributed 10% of total healthcare sectors (**Sanyukta Kanwal, Statista, 18th May 2022**). This study focused on the major contributor i.e., the Hospital segment.

Operators in Hospital sectors: Both State Government and Central Government mostly focus on communicable diseases. The networking of Govt Sectors starts with Primary Health Centres (PHC) & followed by, Sub-division Hospitals (SDH), District Hospitals (DH), Medical colleges & Super-speciality Hospitals. Pvt Players mostly concentrate on non-communicable diseases which are constantly increasing due to rising income, unhealthy lifestyles, and the invention of modern medicines & high-tech medical equipment for early detection & treatment.

2.) The gap in Hospital Beds: In India, we have only 5 hospital beds per 10000 population. Out of 167 countries, only 12 countries are having fewer hospital bed capacities than India.

Rema Nagarajan, TNN, (2020). In addition to the rise of Communicable diseases, the life expectancy at birth is also constantly increasing & in 2020 it was 69.89 as against 66.69 in 2010 (**Statista 2022**). These result in a huge gap in hospital bed capacity in India which we have vividly observed during the Pandemic. Currently, 65% of the total hospital beds of India are concentrated in 7 states i.e., West Bengal, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Telangana, and Uttar Pradesh where 50% of the Indian Population Live & a balance of 35% of beds are spread over to 21 States & 8 Union Territories where the rest of the 50% population live.

3) Challenges:

The challenges of Govt Sectors: There are inherent shortcomings in Infrastructure, Manpower, obscure treatment protocol/services, and excessive patient flow. Only one "Government Hospital" bed is available against the 1844 population. & Only one doctor against 11000 population (**The Print, 23 June 2018**)

There is an overlap of roles & responsibilities as there is no clarity of accountability of sectors starting from PHC to a Super specialty hospital & Medical Colleges in major metro cities. The performance of the sectors gets affected due to any anomaly in the performance of any sectors within the network.

Crisis of Fund: In the Economic Survey of 2022, India's public expenditure on healthcare stood at 2.1% of GDP in 2021-22 against 1.8% in 2020-21 and 1.3% in 2019-20. Govt of India allocated Rs2,34,846 Crore for healthcare for Financial Year 2022(FY22) and also planning to increase the healthcare budget to 2.5% of GDP by 2022 as against the Global Average of 5.4% of GDP.

The hospital authority gets funds for procuring Capital Items for augmenting operation & adding new services but the allocation of fund for the maintenance of the capital items are insignificant compared to the cost of the capital items. As a consequence, after the initial warranty period, most of the equipment becomes inoperative for want of maintenance. High-tech medical equipment gets upgraded due to 1st changing technological advancement. Govt Hospital cannot upgrade their existing systems as they don't have funds for upgradation in addition to the bureaucratic delay in obtaining the approval & special fund for upgradation. These not only affect patient care, but it is also a severe waste of capital investment and precise foreign exchange as high-tech medical equipment is mostly imported.

Crisis of Manpower: There is a severe shortage of Doctors, Nurses, Paramedical staff, and skilled & semi-skilled staff for government hospitals. This shortage is most critical in rural areas as skilled manpower including doctors are reluctant to relocate themselves due to socio-economic reasons. The no of doctors available per 10000 population is 8.6 as against 25-50 for very high human-developed counties (**Human development report 2020**). Nurses are the primary caregivers in rural areas due to the dearth of doctors. This increases the work pressure on the nurses and disturbs their work-life balance & impacting the younger generation's desire to come forward & join the nursing profession resulting in the trap of a demand-supply gap. According to Indian Nursing Council, India has a shortage of 1.94 million nurses despite having 2.34 million nurses (**Asha Mary Raji, May 2021**).

Problems are far deep rooted and comprise social, economic, and political interference ((**Vikas Bajpai,2014**). The dichotomy is, the privileged class fails to understand the societal mind frame of rural areas. They fail to demonstrate that preventive care in a rural area should get equal importance as that of a cure for their own professional reasons. This problem of public hospitals in India is due to the conducive environment for the predominant section of society who are keen to maintain the status quo.

4.) Solution opted for:

Public-Private- Partnership Project (PPP):

To overcome the crisis of Funds, both Capital Expenditure (Capex) & Operational Expenses (Opex), Infrastructure & Manpower, govt institutions both Central & State are now encouraging the participation of Pvt Owners through PPP projects for augmenting their operations. Depending on the risk sharing, investment & responsibility, the most popular PPP models in the healthcare sector are as follows:

- Build Operate & Transfer (BOT), here, the private owner will invest in the project, take responsibility to build, and operate the project for a specific period & earn the revenue from the project during that period & after that transfer the project to the public entity as per the stipulated agreement.
- Establishment, Operation & Maintenance (EOM) Model, in this case, the Pvt partner has to install, operate & maintain the systems at a public institution for a specific contractual period on a revenue-sharing basis with the public entity. A copy of a recent tender notice is attached in Appendix-I.
- Design, Build, Finance, and operate (DBFO), in this model, the Private partner takes full responsibility for the project including Design, Build, Finance, and operation for the contractual period.

5.) Private Hospitals: Govt hospitals' deficiencies in infrastructure, excessive crowds of patients, long queues for getting appointments, particularly for planned surgery, and lack of accountability & apathy of caregivers compel the common people to knock on the door of privately owned hospitals for their treatment & care. There is nexus between caregivers of govt hospitals and private hospitals who regularly refers the patient to Pvt hospitals for their professional interest. A large no of common people has no other choice but to incur huge out-of-pocket expenses (OOP) for their treatment.

The Private Hospital Market in India is expected to reach INR 25429.49 Bn by 2027 with a CAGR of 20.53%, from 2021 (Dublin, Feb 2022/PRNewswire). We all have observed the gap in hospital beds during the pandemic. Existing hospitals & business houses consider the hospital sector as a lucrative business option in India. Govt of India liberalized direct foreign investment (FDI) in the hospital industry. As per **National Institution for Transforming India (NITI)Aayog**, now foreign investors can invest up to 100% in greenfield and up to 74% in brownfield hospital projects. The interest of FDI

can be easily measured with the amount of recent investment, a sum of 7.4 Bn USD has been invested in the Hospital & Diagnostic sector in India between April 2020 & June 2021 (Statista Research Department, Sep 12, 2022)

6.) Literature Review :

Vikas Bajpai (2014), The Challenges Confronting Public Hospitals in India, Their Origins, and Possible Solutions, this article explains the ground reality of public hospitals in India and their challenges with the suggested solution. The study covers a remote Primary Health Centre (PHC) to a tertiary care hospital in a metro city. There should have been a clear demarcation between PHS and tertiary care hospitals but both the hospital practically take care of preventive & curative care. The tertiary hospital is supposed to provide training to PHCs and support them so that they perform their duty as per expectation. Any breakage in this chain impacts the total performance of the Public Healthcare system. The article opined that the major challenges for Public Hospitals are:

"1) deficient infrastructure, (2) deficient manpower, (3) unmanageable patient load, (4) equivocal quality of services, (5) high out-of-pocket expenditure."

The problem starts with the education system which is easily available to the privileged class & difficult for the underprivileged class in rural areas. The action suggested is the active participation of the general mass of society in response to the policies available for the well-being of society and getting the release of healthcare from the clutches of the privileged class.

Statista Research Department (2022), Value of FDI in the healthcare market India 2000-2021, by sector, Statista Research Department, Sep 12, 2022, this article nicely detailed the opportunity of foreign investors in India. According to this study, total healthcare sectors received 28 billion USD between April 2000 to June 2021. Major recipients are, drugs & pharmaceuticals 18.12 bn USD, hospital & diagnostic 7.4 bn USD and medical & surgical appliances 2.2 bn USD.

Research Gap: The figures are not shown year-wise to get a clear picture of the FDI pre & post covid period. **Khushbu B. Thadani (2014)**, this article explained the Public Private Partnership (PPP) models initially & at the global level and then explains the success story of PPP projects in the Healthcare sector of India at the national & state level. The author explained that at the global level, the partnership is usually between a multinational company and an organization engaged in research. An example was cited about the involvement of Bill and Melinda Gates pertinent to the vaccine program. The detailed report cited the involvement of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands in their PPP projects namely the Global Alliance for Vaccine and Immunization (GAVI) in Mozambique, Rwanda, Burundi of Africa, Indonesia, and Mongolia of Asia. The article explains the PPP success story of Mobile Health Vans, Insurance, and Public-Private Partnerships, Remuneration package under the Chiranjeevi Yojana Scheme, etc. The author also referred to the PPP projects pertinent to Lab Instruments, CT scans, MRI, telemedicine, and maintenance services of the hospitals.

Research Gap: The article is silent about the selection procedure of private partners by the Govt entity for the PPP projects.

Asha Mary Reji (2021), this article nicely explains the root cause of the shortage of staff nurses in India. Currently, it states that currently, we have only 1.7 Staff nurses as against the minimum of 3 recommended by the world health organization. According to the author, India is going to be the 2nd largest shortage country in the world after Bangladesh in terms of per-bed staff nurse availability. The article nicely explains the job insecurity & disparity of salary of staff nurses between govt and private sectors prompting them to migrate to other countries. Currently, 6.4lac Indian nurses are working in abroad. Kerala ranks 1st in the migration of skilled nurses abroad from India. The author opined that Govt could have stopped this migration with a better salary, job security & work-life balance.

Research Gap: The article is silent about the comparison of job security & salary of staff nurses who migrated to other countries.

Rema Nagarajan (2021), the author explained the real manpower crisis of Govt Hospitals. During covid, when patients were finding difficulty getting a bed even in privately run small Nursing Homes, beds were empty in the hospital run by Delhi Administration. The real example shared in this article glaringly exposed the caregivers' crisis in govt hospitals. The situation can only change if Govt comes out with a policy for filling the vacancies required based on the no of beds otherwise common people will have no other choice but to get treatment from the Pvt sectors only.

Gap Analysis: The article did not suggest any solution for solving this perennial manpower crisis of Gov hospitals.

Dr. Shenoy Robinson (2017), nicely explains the challenge the hospital industry is to overcome for their revenue growth. His 1st suggestion is instead of buying talent, hospitals should create talent in-house. The article nicely explains hospitals are following the routine way of marketing program to achieve their business target & has the following drawbacks:

- Hospitals are unable to create their own brand for pulling patients on their brand strength.
- Patients are coming to the hospital either through word of mouth or on the credentials of individual Physicians or surgeons.
- The corporate hospitals to date are poaching the top crowd-puller at times even with unrealistic fancy terms.
- Tie up with the local physicians for referring patients to the hospital against handsome commissions nicely coined as referral fees.
- Author also referred to the unethical practice of bringing foreign patients from Delhi International Airport through tout again nicely coined as the facilitator.
- The decision-makers, of the corporate house & public sectors are influenced by the incentives for empanelment followed by offering incentives to Medical Officers to refer patients.
- In the name of CME, entertaining the referrals for getting more patients from them.

The author distinctly stated that the above so-called marketing and outreach program is being followed by all & hence cannot help the hospital to improve its long-term goal of creating its own brand & improved margin.

Research Gap: The article is silent about the apathy of corporate hospitals regarding patient care and the unscrupulous practice of excessive billing in connivance with the insurance company.

7) Research objectives:

The objective of the study is to have a clear understanding of the challenges of the healthcare service delivery industry; analyze the opportunities and suggest a probable action plan to the stakeholders of both public & private sectors for meeting their goal without compromising patient care.

8.) Research Methodology:

The exploratory method has been followed in this study. The study is based on a combination of Qualitative & Quantitative secondary data collected through Extensive Literature reviews, journals, books, and Govt Reports, to explore the research gap pertinent to existing studies.

9.) Analysis:

Govt PPP Projects:

As stated above, to bridge the Gap in infrastructure, Doctors & Staff Nurses, both central & state govt bodies are nowadays inviting private healthcare service delivery players to join hands to augment the operation of govt healthcare service delivery.

Advantages of PPP:

Private sector operators are mostly concentrated in metro cities having their overbearing control over bed capacity, physicians, and staff nurses. The ground reality is Pvt sector holds 78% of beds, 80% of doctors, and 49% of staff nurses in India. Through the PPP model, the huge gap in infrastructure & scarce manpower problems can be addressed particularly in the Rural sector where the crisis is severe. This also will in turn improve the quality of treatment & can reduce the patient referral syndrome from rural hospitals to secondary & tertiary care hospitals in metros.

Disadvantages of PPP a double-edged sword:

The moment a Pvt Owner participates in the cycle with their investment, the commercialization starts which we are vividly observing in Privately managed hospitals. The cost of treatment is exorbitantly high there & the common people without Mediclaim coverage through insurance finding extremely difficult to get treatment there. If govt fails to control the cost of treatment in PPP projects, the below-poverty line people (BPL) will be the worst sufferer both in rural & urban areas. This will defeat the Universal Health Coverage (UHC) mission of India.

There is every possibility of malpractice in selecting private partners for PPP projects. The wrong selection of private partners by corrupt decision-makers will result in procuring substandard equipment & will impact the treatment quality.

PPP Projects in Medical Colleges may impact the learning of medical students as they will not get the opportunity of hands-on training in high-tech medical equipment for the professional interest of Pvt partners. This will impact the treatment capabilities of govt hospitals in the long run.

Challenges of Pvt Hospital:

Along with the lucrative opportunity Pvt sector has to overcome its own struggle. To start a Green Field hospital, the authority has to obtain more than 50 licenses from the different statutory authorities after meeting

stringent rules & regulations. Some of them are not only illogical but impractical also like getting a fire license for obtaining a Trade Licence etc. At times it is very much frustrating for the sectors.

Despite the severe crisis in getting staff nurses in India, the Nursing Council of India recommends recruiting an adequate no of Staff Nurses as detailed in Appendix- II

The disparity in the salary of staff nurses between govt & Pvt sectors also increases the gap in the skilled talent pool.

The high attrition rate of doctors & skilled manpower is a major challenge for almost all hospitals in the Pvt sector.

The fixation of the rate of medical devices by the government of India vis-a-vis the increase of purchase price of medical devices due to INR devaluation against USD impacting the margin of the industry.

Patient satisfaction is the key success factor for hospitals & it is now extremely difficult for hospitals to satisfy the demanding knowledgeable patient.

10.) Conclusions - contribution:

The study will help to understand the ground reality of healthcare delivery in both govt & Pvt sectors. An effort has been made to reveal the practical challenges of Govt Sectors, and the different modalities of Public Private Partnership (PPP) available with a copy of a real Request for Proposal (RFP) of Govt of West Bengal. This will help the Medical Technology companies and the owners of the Pvt sector to understand the Establishment, Operation & Maintenance (EOM) Model. This will also enable them to be thoroughly prepared for participation in future projects. Also tried to explain the shortcomings & commercial traps of PPP projects which public institutions should be aware of & take precautionary measures. The study reveals the huge opportunity lying for women-empowerment to be part of caregivers as staff nurses in India & abroad. There is a shortage of 1.94 million nurses in India itself. The study highlighted the funding opportunity for Pvt sectors through Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). The Pvt sector hospitals prevailing marketing activities have been explained with the suggestion to change their strategy, come out from the traditional way of marketing & implement an out-of-box strategy for improving their business margin for long-term sustainability.

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Appendix-I

GOVERNMENT OF West Bengal Department of Health & Family Welfare

Request for Proposal

Selection of Private Partner for Establishment of 16 slice CT scan services at Government Hospitals under Public Private Partnerships (PPP) – [Number of Call -1st]

(CAPEX & OPEX by Private Partner) Released

on:18.01.2019

Department of Health & Family Welfare Government of West Bengal

Office of Chief Medical Officer of Health

Basirhat Health District

Phone: 03217 265671

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Web site: www.wbhealth.gov.in

Appendix-II

Recommendations of Nursing Staffing Norms by the Staff Inspection Unit:

1.	Normal Wards	1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every 6 beds
2.	Special Wards; Paediatrics Burns/Burns Plastic Neuro Surgery Cardiac Thoracic Neuro Medicine Nursing Home Tetanus Spinal Injury Emergency Wards attached to casual	1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every 4 beds
3.	Nursery	1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every 2 beds
4.	ICU/CCU/ICCR Nephrology (AK Dialysis)	1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every bed
5.	Labour Room	1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every labour table
6.	O.T. Major Minor	2 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every functional operation table including recovery room. 1 Staff Nurse/Nursing Sister for every functional operation table
7.	d) Gynae/Obstetrics Attendance up to 40 patients per day Thereafter for every additional attendance of 15 patients per day	For every additional attendance of 15 patient per day 1 Staff Nurse/ Nursing Sister

8.	O.P.D. (Injection Room) Attendance up to 100 patients per day Attendance up to 120-220 patients per day Attendance up to 221-320 patients per day Attendance up to 321-420 patients per day	Staff Nurse Staff Nurse Staff Nurse Staff Nurse
9.	<u>Name of Deptt.</u> O.P.D. Blood Bank Paediatric Immunization work Eye ENT Pre-Anaesthetic Cardiac Lab. Bronchoscopy Lab Vaccination Anti Rabic Family Planning Medical Surgical Dental Central Sample Collection Centre Orthopaedic Gynae Obstetric Skin V.D. Centre Chemotherapy Neurology Microbiology Infection Control Psychiatry Burns	<u>No. of Staff/Nursing Sister</u> 1 2 2 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 2 1 1 1 1 1 2 2 3 2 2 2 1 2 1 2

In addition to the 10% reserve as per existent rules, 45% posts may be added for offs also where services are provided for 365 days in a year.